

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Sherzod Mirmakhmudov

**METHODS AND PROCEDURES AIMED AT GUARANTEEING THE
IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNATIONAL TREATIES**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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2023/AVGUST

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MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

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